

SOME ASPECTS OF THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE PERMIT SYSTEM IN THE FIELD OF ECOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10628396>

Today, a number of reforms are being implemented in our country with the aim of reducing mandatory requirements and simplifying licensing and permitting procedures through regulatory impact assessment. In particular, in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 8, 2024 "On measures to reduce mandatory requirements in the field of entrepreneurship and simplify licensing and permitting procedures" No. PF-8 from March 1, 2024:

when 50% of the amount of the fine imposed on legal entities for committing offenses in the field of licensing, permitting and notification procedures is voluntarily paid within fifteen days, and 70% within thirty days, the offender is exempted from paying the rest of the fine;

in the process of issuing a document with the nature of a license or permission, a procedure for remote assessment of applicants' compliance with the requirements and conditions of documents with the nature of a license and permission is introduced using video communication tools;

during the state registration or re-registration of a business entity, it is allowed to indicate the residence of the founder as its postal address.

It should be noted that ensuring transparency in the permitting system, limiting the powers of government officials, and reducing the human factor in granting permits are of great importance in ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens.

The analysis of legal literature shows that many scholars show that the permit system is an important component of public administration and its leading function.

Y.Starilov states that the authorization system is a set of normatively regulated social relations that arise in connection with the issuance of permits for the implementation of certain types of activities and the subsequent implementation of state control over the observance of the rules and conditions

of the implementation of permitted activities, and that it has the following forms shows:

- 1) Special permit;
- 2) License;
- 3) Certificate;
- 4) Act of accreditation;
- 5) Qualification certificate;
- 6) Certificate;
- 7) Quota;
- 8) Right to control¹.

D. Bahrakh also emphasizes this point and states that the purpose of the authorization system is to ensure the safety of the state, society and citizens².

Based on the analysis of the opinions of the above scientists, we can emphasize that the permit system is a set of tools for state management bodies to permit individuals and legal entities to engage in certain activities and to exercise control over their activities based on the permit requirements.

It should be noted that the liberalization of the permit system does not show its effectiveness in all areas. In particular, the deterioration of the existing ecological situation in our country requires strict measures by the water regulatory bodies. Because in the ranking of the Welfare Index for 2023 maintained by the Legatum Institute of Great Britain, the Republic of Uzbekistan is listed in the lowest places³.

Today, the number of violations in the field of ecology and damage to nature in our country is greater than ever. The analysis of statistical data shows that the amount of damage caused to nature as a result of violations in the field of ecology is constantly increasing. In particular, in 2022, in 1,409 cases, 5.8 billion soums of fines and materials were sent to law enforcement agencies to collect damage to nature and take legal action. Criminal cases were opened in 36 cases.

More than 300 objects of the animal world, 6442 kg of medicinal, technical and nutritious plants, 2433 kg of fish products, more than 550 inventories were seized from the offenders in the prescribed manner.

446 economic entities were inspected under the state environmental control procedure, 379 cases of law violations were detected, and a fine of 437.8

¹ Общее административное право : учебник : в 2 ч. / под ред. Ю. Н. Старилова ; Воронежский государственный университет. – 2-е изд., пересмотр. и доп. – Воронеж : Издательский дом ВГУ, 2016. - с 651.

² Административное право: учебник / Д. Н. Бахрах, Б. В. Россинский, Ю.Н. Старилов. — 3-е изд., пересмотр. и доп. — М.: Норма, 2008. — 816 с.

³ <https://www.prosperity.com/about/resources>

million soums was imposed. Additional compensation payments of 50.2 billion soums were calculated for environmental pollution.

The activity of 24 enterprises that did not comply with environmental requirements was temporarily suspended by court decision until the shortcomings were eliminated.

4,673 cases of illegal cutting of trees and bushes in the territories, as well as damage to them, were detected, fines of more than 7 billion soums and damage to nature more than 10 billion soums were calculated⁴.

These data are only the cases identified by the competent authorities, and there are many cases of violations that have been overlooked.

In our opinion, the increase in violations of the law in the field of natural resource use and environmental protection is due to the liberality of the permit system in the field.

In particular, in accordance with the first paragraph of the sixth paragraph of the Decree No. PF-6044 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 25, 2020 "On measures to radically improve the procedures for licensing and permitting", issuing licenses by competent authorities, extending their validity period and renewing them it is forbidden to refuse to provide public services due to the existence of debts of the license applicant for electricity, natural gas supply, water supply and drainage services, solid household waste collection and removal services, as well as due to executive documents.

The existence of this norm is intended to create a wide opportunity for business entities, but it will negatively affect the quality of services of collection and removal of solid domestic waste, which has a negative impact on the environment, and will lead to their accumulation. In our opinion, it is appropriate to cancel this norm. Because environmental protection, rational use of natural resources and ensuring the ecological safety of the population are the main directions of the environmental policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to Article 49 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, everyone has the right to have a comfortable environment, reliable information about its condition, and the state implements measures to improve, restore and protect the environment, maintain ecological balance, in accordance with the principle of sustainable development.

An important role is played by the effective and effective activity of state management bodies regulating the field in the provision of environmental rights

⁴ <https://kun.uz/news/2023/02/11/2022-yilda-tabiatga-yetkazilgan-zarar-uchun-40-mlrd-som-jarima-tayinlandi> 20.

of citizens. Therefore, it is appropriate to revise the legal documents regulating this activity and establish strict norms.

References:

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